

Ion-Solvent Interaction of Biunivalent Salts in Mixed Solvents at 35°

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Viscosity, apparent molar volume and conductance of CdCl_2 , CdBr_2 , $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in dioxane+water, glycerol+water, glycol+water and methanol+water at different compositions have been studied at 35°, the ion-solvent interactions have been inferred and the order is $\text{MeOH}+\text{water} > \text{dioxane}+\text{water} > \text{glycol}+\text{water} > \text{glycerol}+\text{water}$.

VISCOSITY, apparent molar volume and conductance of electrolytic solutions in aquo-organic solvents have been studied with a view to understand the nature of the ion-ion and ion-solvent interaction¹. In the present communication, these properties of CdCl_2 , CdBr_2 , $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in dioxane+water, glycerol+water, glycol+water and methanol+water (10, 20 and 30% by wt.) at 35° have been studied, and an attempt has been made to deal with the nature of ion-solvent interaction and hydrogen bonding on the above properties.

Experimental

All the salts used were of E. Merck 'extra pure' variety. The apparatus, technique, and preparation of solvents and solutions were the same as reported earlier¹. The concentration range of the viscosity and apparent molar volume was from 0.1–0.0025 mol dm⁻³ and 0.02–0.004 mol dm⁻³, respectively, for conductance measurements. The time flow did not exceed 0.2 s in 15 min; the density data being accurate up to ±0.0002 g and conductance data ±2 in 1000.

Results and Discussion

Viscosity: The viscosity data were analysed in terms of modified Jones-Dole equation²,

$$\eta_r = 1 + A\sqrt{\alpha C} + B\alpha C$$

where α is the degree of dissociation calculated from conductance data. The B values were obtained from the equation,

$$\eta_r - 1 - A\sqrt{\alpha C}/C = (B_{MA^+} + B_{A^-}) + \alpha(B_{M^{2+}} + B_{A^{2-}} - B_{MA^+})$$

and are presented in Table 1. The positive B values indicate strong alignment of solvent molecules with the ions which undoubtedly promotes the structure of the solvent molecules in its immediate vicinity. The smaller the value of B the greater in the ion-solvent interaction³. From Table 1 it is observed that ion-solvent interaction order is $\text{methanol}+\text{water} > \text{dioxane}+\text{water} > \text{glycol}+\text{water} > \text{glycerol}+\text{water}$.

B -coefficient is found to increase with the increase in organic solvent. This is attributed due to the larger size of the molecules and also due to strong association through hydrogen bonding³. For larger solvated ions, would lead to larger values of η^E , the positive increase owing to shape and size of an ion, and η^A the alignment owing to orientation of the polar molecules due to ionic field. Consequently, $\eta^E + \eta^A > \eta^D$, where η^D is the decrease in viscosity arising due to distortion of the solvent structure by the ions and hence the B -coefficient becomes larger with the increase in organic solvent⁴.

Apparent molar volume: The apparent molar volume are calculated in the usual manner⁵. The data obtained have been found to agree with Massin's equations, $\phi = \phi^0 + S_v\sqrt{C}$, as the plot of ϕ vs $C^{1/2}$ is linear. The limiting apparent molar volume from the intercept are presented in Table 1. Limiting slope is found for S_v to be positive (not shown) in all cases showing the ion-ion interaction. The ϕ^0 is found to be of the order, $\text{MeOH}+\text{water} > \text{dioxane}+\text{water} > \text{glycol}+\text{water} > \text{glycerol}+\text{water}$ for all the four salts which indicate the order of the ion-solvent interaction⁶. The ϕ^0 also increase with the increase of organic solvents and is attributed to be due to ionic solvation.

Conductivity: The ion association of these electrolytes has been studied and the dissociation constants have been calculated in the usual manner⁷,

TABLE 1—VALUES OF B AND ϕ° OF THE SALTS IN DIFFERENT WEIGHT PERCENT OF SOLVENT SYSTEMS

	Dioxane+ Water			Glycerol + Water			Glycol + Water			MeOH + Water		
	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%
B values ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)												
CdCl ₂	0.18	0.40	0.47	0.35	0.59	0.69	0.30	0.50	0.60	0.14	0.25	0.38
CdBr ₂	0.16	0.37	0.45	0.33	0.58	0.67	0.29	0.49	0.58	0.13	0.24	0.37
Cd(NO ₃) ₂	0.19	0.41	0.49	0.39	0.62	0.69	0.33	0.52	0.61	0.15	0.27	0.40
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	0.27	0.38	0.56	0.41	0.54	0.62	0.36	0.48	0.55	0.24	0.27	0.34
ϕ° values ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)												
CdCl ₂	30.8	32.8	35.6	26.7	29.6	30.9	28.7	31.8	33.7	32.5	34.7	37.8
CdBr ₂	32.8	34.8	36.9	28.7	30.3	32.8	29.7	31.7	33.7	34.7	37.0	38.9
Cd(NO ₃) ₂	36.7	38.3	40.9	39.4	42.5	48.8	37.3	38.7	40.8	39.6	39.3	40.2
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	37.2	39.3	42.4	40.5	44.6	50.3	37.8	38.4	36.6	36.10	37.6	37.4

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $-\Delta G_i$ (J mol^{-1}) OF SALTS IN DIFFERENT WEIGHT PERCENTAGE OF SOLVENTS

	Dioxane+ Water			Glycerol + Water			Glycol + Water			MeOH + Water		
	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%
CdCl ₂	300	650	1 060	502	1 248	1 590	450	1 000	1 380	270	750	970
CdBr ₂	410	820	1 680	683	1 287	2 250	620	1 260	1 850	550	1 090	1 666
Cd(NO ₃) ₂	640	1 950	2 000	840	1 487	2 325	730	1 380	2 110	640	840	1 560
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	334	687	1 086	885	1 767	2 345	757	1 648	2 155	483	1 187	1 725

from which the standard thermodynamic quantity (ΔG_i°) from water to organic solvent + water mixture could be calculated by Feakin⁸ method. These values are recorded in Table 2 and are all negative. The greater the ΔG_i° (since negative) the greater is the ion-ion interaction and lesser is the ion-solvent interaction. So the ion-solvent interaction is of the order, methanol + water > dioxane + water > glycol + water > glycerol + water. This can be explained as follows. Dioxane because of its bulk size is unable to be accommodated in the solvent structure and hence causing a breakdown in the three-dimensional water structure. Amongst glycerol, glycol and methanol, glycerol has the tendency to break the hydrogen bond more readily than methanol, and glycol being in between these two. But from the above three properties, the reverse is seen to be

true. This is probably due to the low ion-solvent dipole interaction energy, which is unable to break the strong inter-molecular hydrogen bond.

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